

IC Modelling and Analysis in Geotechnical Engineering

Flow Model 01

Contents:

IC MAGE FM01 is a user-defined flow model for PLAXIS that allows the simulation of spatially-varying anisotropic permeability.

Disclaimer:

IC MAGE soil models undergo extensive testing and validation but can never be guaranteed to be free of errors. IC MAGE soil models are employed at the users' own risk and the authors of these models cannot be held responsible or liable for any errors arising from their application.

Document history:

Date	Revision	
2023-04-04	1.0	Initial publication

How to cite:

Taborda, DMG, Kontoe, S, Tsiampousi, A (2023) "IC MAGE Flow Model 01 – Nonlinearly varying anisotropic permeability (Version 1.0)". Zenodo.

doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7796383](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796383)

IC MAGE FM01

Nonlinearly varying anisotropic permeability

PLUGIN FILE FORMAT

```
{“material”:      N,
“file”:          “ic_mage_fm01_64.dll”,
“model”:         “ic_mage_fm01”,
“replace”:       “saturated_permeability”,
“parameters”:   [P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6],
“state_variables”: []}
```

where N is the material number, see usage notes for guidance

PARAMETER LIST

P1	a		Rate of variation of $\log_{10} k$ with coordinates
P2	b		$\log_{10} k$ for a coordinate value equal to $P5 c_{ref}$
P3	r	> 0	Anisotropy ratio
P4	k_{min}	≥ 0	Minimum permeability
P5	c_{ref}		Reference coordinate
P6	c_{switch}	1, 2, 3	Switch defining the axis used for the reference coordinate: 1 – x -axis, 2 – y -axis, 3 – z -axis

STATE VARIABLES

This model does not employ state variables

MODEL FORMULATION

The permeability along the main axis of the analysis (defined using $P6$) is given by:

$$\log_{10} k_I = a \cdot (c - c_{ref}) + b \geq \log_{10} k_{min} \quad (1)$$

where c is the coordinate along the chosen axis (i.e. coordinate x for $P6 c_{switch} = 1$, coordinate y for $P6 c_{switch} = 2$ and coordinate z for $P6 c_{switch} = 3$).

The permeability along the two other axes perpendicular to the coordinate axis c is then given by:

$$k_{II} = k_{III} = r \cdot k_I \quad (2)$$

For example, if $P6 c_{switch} = 2$, then $k_I = k_y$ and $k_{II} = k_{III} = k_x = k_z$.

MODEL USAGE

1. the units used in the parameter list provided through the plugin file are **always** kN (force), day (time), m (space) and K (temperature).

2. the material number can be obtained by using the command 'echo materials' and counting only the soil materials listed in the table. Note that material numbers in UDFMs start at 1 (rather than 0 as in the GUI).

TYPICAL PARAMETERS

The permeability profiles for London Clay used by Avgerinos (2014) to reproduce the field data shown by Hight et al. (2007) can be achieved using the following set of parameters:

$$P_1 = 0.0215, \quad P_2 = -4.5259, \quad P_3 = 2.0, \quad P_4 = 8.64 \times 10^{-8}, \quad P_5 = c_{ref}, \quad P_6 = 2.0$$

assuming that the vertical direction is given by the y -axis (hence $P_6 = 2.0$) and the value of $P_5 c_{ref}$ is the y -coordinate of the top of London Clay.

REFERENCES

Avgerinos, V. (2014) Numerical investigation of tunnelling beneath existing tunnels. PhD Thesis, Imperial College London, UK.

Hight, D.W., Gasparre, A., Nishimura, S., Minh, N.A., Jardine, R.J., Coop, M.R. (2007) Characteristics of the London Clay from the terminal 5 site at Heathrow airport. *Géotechnique*, Vol.57, No.1, pp.: 3–18.